

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Pyrolytic Graphite Foils and TPS

The following application highlight addresses the in-plane thermal conductivity of the Pyrolytic Graphite Foils (900-1800 W/mK), characterized using the C-Therm TPS Module with the Slab Utility.

Graphite is a crystalline form of carbon that are naturally occurring and synthesized from non-graphitic carbon. Both synthetic and natural graphite are consumed in large quantities, with a wide variation in commercial space, such as lubricants, electrodes, thermal management, and sealants.

Figure 1 In-plane thermal conductivity correlation with microstructure of carbon-based materials.

Synthetic graphite is typically obtained by pyrolysis (high heat, no oxygen) of non-graphitic carbons (e.g., hydrocarbons – methane, ethane, etc.). Highly Oriented Pyrolytic Graphite is synthesized with additional tensile stress in the basal-plane direction, improving the graphitic crystals' alignment and interlayer contact, Figure 1. Variability in the manufacturing process (expansion, compression, rolling, deposition) can have a major impact on the anisotropy (in-plane >> through-plane) and thermal properties of the foil. Higher thermal conductivity can be achieved by densifying the foils, attributed to microstructure (crystallinity) improvement and decreasing overall phonon scattering.¹

Figure 2 C-Therm 30 mm Thermal Conductivity Sensor.

The FLEX Transient Plane Source (TPS) method available on the Trident platform has been used to measure the in-plane thermal conductivity of the natural graphite sheets and the pyrolytic

¹E. Solfiti, F. Berto, Procedia Struct. Integr., A review on thermophysical properties of flexible graphite, 26, 187-198 (2020).

graphite sheets using the Slab Utility, Figure 2. The 30mm TPS sensor was placed between two identical graphite foils and then stacked on bulk insulations (EPS board) on both sides. The setup is then clamped down using a vice to minimize the error via contact resistances between the sensor-sample interface.

The graphite foils were provided by HPMS Graphite and shown in Figure 3 are the measured thermal conductivity of the pyrolytic graphite foils (HGS) as a function of density. In this case, the trend where a higher thermal conductivity correlates with thinner and denser pyrolytic graphite foil is observed. For example, the k of HGS-012 (12 μm thickness, $\rho = 2.27 \text{ g/cm}^3$) was measured to be 1786 W/mK while the HGS-70 (70 μm thickness, $\rho = 1.48 \text{ g/cm}^3$) measured k is 952 W/mK. Similar trends are reported with flexible graphite foils as measured by the TPS method (not shown), although in a much lower thermal conductivity range.²

Figure 3 In-plane Thermal Conductivity of Flexible and Pyrolytic Graphite Foils vs density.

In summary, the strong relation between density and thermal conductivity has been elucidated by Trident’s FLEX TPS method, using the Slab utility. Worth noting is the measurement of thermal conductivity of pyrolytic graphite foils (HGS-12, 12 μm , k = 1786 W/mK) using the TPS method is unprecedented at the time this application note was written.

To learn more about C-Therm’s Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com

² Cermak, M., Perez, N., Collins, M. *et al.*, *Material properties and structure of natural graphite sheet*. Sci Rep 10, 18672 (2020).